

Agriculture Scenario And Strength For Development In Muzaffarpur District

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Abstract Agriculture is the main occupation of the people of Muzaffarpur district in Bihar, which employing 77% of the total population which is generating 35% of the state domestic product. Muzaffarpur is a district in Bihar, which is known as the land of Litchi, was created in 1875 for administrative purpose. Now, Muzaffarpur district is a part of Tirhut Division with 88% of the state's poor living in rural areas, improving livelihoods and reducing poverty. Major crops grown in Muzaffarpur are Paddy, Wheat, Maize, Sugarcane, Potato, and other vegetables. The Agricultural sector in Muzaffarpur is faces lot of trouble with numerous, and new known constraints and problems. The present paper discusses the issues and problems faced by the Agricultural Sector in Muzaffarpur District, Bihar and talks about the possible strategic interventions to make the best use of available resources adopting a multi-Pronged strategy of development. It also talks about the area specific problems and suggests way and means to solve them easily and short out the problems and issues faced in agricultural development in Muzaffarpur district.

Keywords Muzaffarpur, Kharif, Rabi, Vegetation.

Introduction

Muzaffarpur is located at 26⁰07' N 85⁰24' E. The city lies in a highly active seismic zone of India. Muzaffarpur district occupies an area of 3175.9 square kilometre (1226.2 sq. mi). According to 2011 Census Muzaffarpur district has a population of 48, 01,062 . The district has a population density of 1514 inhabitants per square kilometre (3920/sq. mi). Its population growth rate over the decade 2001 to 2011 was 28.14%.

Muzaffarpur has a sex ratio of 900 females for every 1000 males, And a literacy rate of 63.4%. Scheduled caste and scheduled tribes make up 15.66% and 0.12% of the population respectively.

Muzaffarpur has a humid subtropical climate under the Koppen's climatic classification. The summer, between April and June, Each extremely hot and humid (28-40⁰c, 90% max), and in winter is pleasantly cool around 6 to 20 degrees Celsius. Rainfall in Muzaffarpur City is comparatively less compared to the other part of Bihar. Agriculture is the main occupation of the district. The soil of the district is highly calcareous. Paddy is the main crop of the district which accounts for the major portion of the green area zone followed by maize.

Map of Muzaffarpur District

Objective of study

1. To develop the agricultural sector through the help of Government funds.
2. Muzaffarpur has many agricultural lands which needs the support of farmers to farming and skilled workforce for enhancement of food security.
3. The development of agricultural land is very necessary for fooding, shelter, clothing, medicines etc.
4. The farmers of Muzaffarpur needs the funds security for the better result of farming from which they secure about their hardwork.

Review of Literature

Muzaffarpur district comprises of big agricultural land which needs group of farmers for farming. Many types of items grown here in huge amount, but it needs a good support for the cultivation. Agriculture of Bihar by P Dayal, also focuses on that many problems facing by farmers for cultivation. The soil of Muzaffarpur district is very good for the cultivation of many types of food items.

Main Text

Agricultural scenario

Agriculture is the core of Muzaffarpur’s as well as Bihar’s economy, employing 77% of the workforce and generating 35% of the state domestic product.

Agricultural seasons are identified on the basis of sowing and harvesting of particular crops virtually agriculture season is crop season. Here four agricultural seasons have been identified namely Bhadai, Aghani, Rabi and Garma. The Bhadai and Aghani crops are also known as Kharif crops.

SI No.	Agricultural Seasons	Period	Important Crops
1.	Kharif	May to November	Paddy, Ragi, Millet, Maize, Groundnut, Jwar, Bazra, Til.
a.	Bhadai	May to August	Paddy, Maize, Millet, Jude
b.	Aghani	July to November	Paddy, Sugarcane

2.	Rabi	November to March	Wheat, Gram, Mustard, Lentils.
3.	Garma	April to June	Paddy, Onion, Maize, Vegetables

Agriculture being the main occupation of the people, Rice is the main crop of the district accounting for the major portion of the grown area sown. Maize and Wheat is the next important crop of the district. Sugarcane, potato and badly are some of the cereal crops grown. The district is famous for Litchi and Mango which are supplied to other state as well.

However litchi laced with GI tag, and the associate processed product offers the district advantage over other produce due to its unique variety shahi-litchi known worldwide.

However the agricultural sector in Muzaffarpur is plagued with numerous and well known constraints and problems this include:

1. Extremely volatile agricultural output mainly due to Socks from regular monsoon flooding in some parts of the district and periodic drought in others.
2. Low productivity average yield of rice and wheat the two most widely cultivated crops are 20 to 25% less than the average.
3. Poorly developed rural roads infrastructure.
4. Floods, waterlogging, poor drainage, and inadequate public investments on expanding and maintaining surface integration systems.
5. Access to electricity in limited to only 5% of ruler households compared to 44% nationally lack of rural electrification is a formidable barrier to both farm and non-farm development.
6. Farmers without access to surface irrigation must rely mainly on desired rather than electricity to tap groundwater sources which rises production costs and effects comparativeness.
7. Public research and extension services suffer from a variety of familiar ills Including lack of strategic focus, thin dispersal of available resources, and inability to effectively utilize available staff due to limited operation budgets.
8. Lack of high quality seeds,, the quality of seeds used in farming is essential in attaining a higher crop yield.
9. One of the major problems faced by farmers is the lack of adequate farm equipment which can hamper their ability to adapt to the requirement of modern farming practices.
10. Inadequate market linkages, farmers often lack access to reliable and transport markets, which results in low price for their products.

Horticultural Scenario

Horticulture has emerged as one of the most important agricultural enterprises in Bihar in the last two decades, as it offers a wide range of opportunities for farmers to diversify their cropping pattern to include fruits, vegetables, flowers, spices, plantation crops, medicinal and aromatic plants. The increasing diversification provides opportunities for absorption of labour and earning remunerative returns to the farmers. The horticultural products form an important component of food and nutritional security in Bihar. To meet the growing demand for affordable and high-quality fruits in local, national, and international markets, this sector is experiencing substantial competition. Since horticultural crops are highly perishable and seasonal in nature, they require adequate post-harvest infrastructure. The State Government is promoting horticulture sector in a big way in Muzaffarpur to help the farmers.

Though State is one of the largest producers of various Fruits & Vegetables however due to lack of various post-harvest management infrastructures, there is considerable volume loss. This is not only commodity loss but also has considerable impact on farmer/producers of Fruits &Vegetables who have to make immediate sale of the produce due to the low shelf life and lack of any storage infrastructures. The key reasons driving the huge volume of wastages are poor post-harvest system, inefficient supply chains, lack of proper storage and processing infrastructure.

1. **Minimizing Loss:** The structure would support better handling practices, storage through cold rooms, thus helping in minimizing the losses.
2. **Cost reduction:** The structure would help in minimizing costs of wastages and other handling costs through promoting value creation and storage.
3. **Value creation:** The structure would promote post-harvest management practices through ensuring proper sorting, grading and packaging, substantially higher values can be realized from marketing of processed commodities.
4. **Ensured Quality:** The structure will have various units in the form of cold room, waxing, packaging house etc. which would ensure quality of the produce and high shelf-life.
5. **Maintains the commodity market price:** The storage helps in normalizing the price of crops throughout the year through the making available quality produce during lean period ensuring uninterrupted supply and thereby minimizing food inflation.
6. **Enhanced market linkage:** It empowers farmers with the ability to capture a larger buyer base and helps to bring their harvest to more valuable.

Brief Details

Primary Processing such as-washing, cleaning, sorting, grading, waxing and packing lines is an important component of Pack House. These components add shelf life to the products and ease the handling by packing into smaller and big packs as required. These systems alone can bring significant reduction in spoilage. Also, in most cases well-packaged products will attract better prices.

Production of Fruits & Vegetables in Muzaffarpur

1. Fruits

a) **Mango:** Mango constitutes the largest area under fruit cultivation in Muzaffarpur. The key varieties such as - Jardalu Aam, Maldah Aam are some of the famous varieties cultivated in the State. Jardalu Mango has been GI tagged.

b) Litchi: Bihar is the leading producer of Litchi in the country contributing almost half the total national production. Muzaffarpur is the largest Litchi producing district followed by Vaishali, Sitamarhi, East Champaran and Madhubani.

c) Banana: Banana is the third largest growing fruits in State in terms of area and cultivated in an area of 0.34 lakh Ha with a production of 13.68 lakh tons. It constitutes an area of 10.8% under fruits and 32.2% of total fruit production. Katihar, Muzaffarpur, Samastipur, Vaishali and Darbhanga are top five producing regions of Banana in addition to other districts.

d) Guava: Guava is cultivated in area of 0.29 lakh Ha with a total production of 4.34 lakh tons constituting about 9.2% and 10.2% to the total area and production of fruits in Bihar. Nalanda, Muzaffarpur, Patna , Rohtas and Vaishali are top five producing districts of guava in the State

Fruits	Area (Ha)	Production (MT)
Amla/Gooseberry	2207.5	16578.34
Banana	34973.45	1368548.76
Guava	29777	434076.59
Limes and Lemons	19365.75	115084.08
Litchi	36263.78	307996.67
Mango	160242.16	1541286.68
Muskmelon	3129.85	16714.14
Papaya	2572.25	47939.07
Pineapple	4245.5	111890.50
Sweet Orange /Mosambi	445	4645.00
Watermelon	2352.5	36143.60
Other Citrus	29014.23	255309.99
Total	324588.97	4256213.42

2. Vegetables

- a) **Potato:** Bihar is one of the leading producers of potato in the country and the crop constitutes largest area and production among all other vegetables. Patna, Nalanda, Begusarai, Bhagalpur, Darbhanga, Katihar, Madhubani, Muzaffarpur, East and West Champaran, Nalanda, Purnia, Rohtas, Samastipur, Sitamarhi and Vaishali are top 15 producing districts of potato in the State.
- b) **Brinjal:** Though brinjal is cultivated across the State among all districts- Vaishali, Patna, Muzaffarpur, Begusarai and Darbhanga are major cultivating regions of brinjal in State.
- c) **Tomato:** Tomato is cultivated in an area of 0.52 lakh Ha with a total production of 9.64 lakh tons, which constitutes about 6.3% and 5.9% of the total area and production of vegetables in State. Patna, Vaishali, Begusarai, Nalanda and Muzaffarpur are major production regions of tomato in the State.
- d) **Bottle Guard:** The total area under bottle guard cultivation in the State was 0.44 lakh Ha with a total production of 6.61 lakh tons which constitute about 5.3% and 4% of total area and production under vegetable in State. Vaishali, Muzaffarpur, Sitamarhi, West Champaran and Katihar are the major producing districts of bottle guard in State.

Conclusion The development of agricultural lands are increasing day by day as per government norms and the farmers also trying their best for the best cultivation in next coming years, which increases the economy of the district. Government related funds provide the farmers to increase their cultivation and improves the area of cultivation .

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